

Letter

An ultrasonic metamaterial based on the two-dimensional Lieb lattice structure

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ABSTRACT

Flat-band (FB) metamaterials offer a unique opportunity for controlling acoustic energy through geometry-induced wave-localization rather than material contrast. We experimentally realise a two-dimensional polymer Lieb lattices that support compact-localized-states (CLS) at ultrasonic frequencies. Guided by a tight-binding (TB) analysis, the structures are fabricated using high-resolution 3D printing, enabling precise reproduction of the three-site Lieb geometry at millimetre scales relevant to sub-MHz ultrasonics.

The vibrational response at individual lattice sites has been directly measured using broadband ultrasonic excitation and scanning Laser-Doppler-Vibrometry. The experiments reveal site-selective wave-localization consistent with CLS formation predicted by the TB model. A comparison between two fabricated lattices demonstrates geometric scaling of the FB frequency in agreement with TB expectations. Full-wave finite-element simulations reproduce the band topology and real-space eigenmodes.

Our results establish that FB physics can be realised robustly in 3D-printed, polymer-based acoustic lattices in sub-MHz regime, enabling applications in ultrasonic imaging, energy trapping, and sensing applications.

1. Introduction

The interaction of waves with periodic structures is a fundamental topic in condensed matter and wave physics [1]. The periodic arrangement of material properties gives rise to Bloch modes [2], leading to the formation of energy bands that determine how waves propagate through the medium. These band structures define regions of allowed and forbidden frequencies, known as band gaps, where transmission is possible or suppressed, respectively. Such band phenomena were first established in electronic systems [1,3] and later extended to classical wave systems, including fluid-mechanical [4], photonic [3,5] and phononic crystals (PnCs) [6], in which periodic modulation of refractive index and elastic properties enables precise control over light and sound propagation, respectively.

The development of such artificially structured media, with tailored dispersion and effective parameters not attainable in natural materials, has led to the development of *metamaterials* [7]. By designing the geometry, symmetry, and coupling within periodic architectures, metamaterials can exhibit unconventional phenomena such as negative refraction [8], topologically protected edge states [9], and robust wave transport

immune to backscattering [10]. These advances have provided new experimental platforms for exploring topology-driven wave dynamics and reconfigurable band-structure engineering.

Certain lattice geometries can give rise to a particularly striking feature, namely the emergence of *flat bands* (FBs) [11,12]. These bands are dispersionless across the Brillouin zone; since the group velocity $v_g = \frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{\partial E(\mathbf{k})}{\partial \mathbf{k}}$ vanishes everywhere, and the effective mass $m^* \propto \left(\frac{\partial^2 E(\mathbf{k})}{\partial k^2} \right)^{-1}$ diverges, the quasiparticles can be regarded as having an infinitely large effective mass [1]. FBs arise from *compact localized states* (CLSs) [13], as can be seen readily within the *tight-binding* (TB) framework [1]. For such CLSs, destructive interference between hopping paths confines eigenstates to a small cluster of sites. As a result, these modes remain spatially localized without dispersion, independent of \vec{k} [6,14]. The FBs coexist with dispersive bands in geometries such as the so-called stub, kagome [15], dice [16], and Lieb lattices [17,18]. FB systems can be systematically engineered by adjusting lattice geometry, symmetry, and material properties, allowing manipulation of wave propagation in photonic [13,17–20], and electronic systems [21,22] and also many other experimentally relevant systems [23–28].

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The realization of FBs has also opened new pathways for controlling acoustic signals [29,30]. In these systems, defects or resonant cavities can be arranged in periodic lattices whose effective couplings mirror those of TB models [29,31]. However, most experimental realisations to date rely on defect lattices embedded within a larger phononic crystal. In these designs [29,32–34], the underlying crystal is acoustically rigid at the frequencies of interest, creating a well-defined bandgap. FBs emerge by removing these individual rigid structures from an otherwise periodic rigid-cell PnC. The resulting spaces act as isolated defect cavities, and their weak evanescent coupling through the surrounding medium leads to a TB-like band structure. Crucially, these defect lattices contain no exclusive physical connecting pathways between sites; instead, coupling occurs only through the host medium, and FB behaviour relies on the existence of a bandgap in the parent PnC.

In contrast, the present work investigates a true Lieb lattice constructed directly as a polymer network, where cylindrical resonators are physically connected by thin elastic struts. Our lattice consists of periodic repetitions of a three-site unit cell, and the coupling is mediated mechanically through continuous elastic pathways and not through removed-rod defects embedded in a bandgap. This distinction enables us to realise FB physics without requiring a surrounding phononic crystal, and to do so at ultrasonic frequencies using 3D-printed polymer structures. The diagonal spacing between Lieb sites is chosen to favor interference-dominated confinement within the operating frequency range.

By fabricating two geometrically-scaled versions of this polymer Lieb lattice and probing their vibrational response using scanning laser Doppler vibrometry, we demonstrate direct experimental observation of FB localization. These measurements, supported by TB modelling and full-wave COMSOL simulations, confirm the presence of CLSs and illustrate how geometric scaling tunes the FB frequency.

By working directly at ultrasonic frequencies, the structures presented one of the first experimentally accessible polymer based realisations of acoustic Lieb lattices in the ultrasonic regime. This frequency range is particularly relevant for biomedical ultrasound and sensing applications including therapeutic ultrasound [35], ultrasound-mediated drug delivery [36], and elastography-based tissue characterization [37], where controlled energy localisation and frequency selectivity may be desirable [38–40]. Together, these results establish polymer Lieb lattices as a practical route toward compact, frequency-selective acoustic components that could be integrated into future applications such as ultrasonic imaging, diagnostic, and sensing technologies.

2. Experimental design considerations

2.1. Design strategy for a 2D acoustic Lieb lattice in the ultrasonic regime

As stated above, there is interest in designing a device that has the potential to work in the ultrasound regime. The (~ 100 kHz – 1 MHz) frequency range was chosen for this study, as the resulting wavelengths were large enough to allow 3D printing of the required geometry, and still be compatible with standard ultrasonic transducers and vibrometry systems. Previous demonstrations in *defect lattices* for example, Ma et al. [29], use “defects” of air in a matrix of steel rods. Here, we shall proceed more directly by constructing lattices in which the material supporting the sound propagation, including the propagation channels, is built up directly as a polymer matrix. This strategy is enabled by the widespread availability of 3D printing techniques.

It is first necessary to define the lattice parameters. In Fig. 1b, we show a schematic diagram of the 2D Lieb lattice. The Lieb lattice can be thought of as either (i) a regular 2D square lattice with additional inter-site Lieb lattices added or equivalently as (ii) a 2D square lattice with always one lattice site of a 2×2 plaquette removed consistently for all plaquettes. Therefore, the band structure of the resulting periodic lattice

in the TB description is well known to be [16,18,29]

$$f_0(\vec{k}) = f_0, \quad f_{\pm}(\vec{k}) = f_0 \pm \gamma \sqrt{4 + 2 \cos(k_x a) + 2 \cos(k_y a)}, \quad (1)$$

where γ is the nearest-neighbour hopping strength representing the acoustic coupling between neighbouring lattice sites, $\vec{k} = (k_x, k_y)$ and a the length of a unit cell (cf. Appendix A). The three bands $f_0(\vec{k})$, $f_+(\vec{k})$, and $f_-(\vec{k})$ stem from the 3-sites in the primitive unit cell indicated in Fig. 1c and its corresponding 3D representation is shown in Fig. 1a.

The central FB $f_0(\vec{k})$ is induced by the existence of CLSs [13,17]. These consist of an alternating non-zero set of amplitudes ± 1 at the Lieb sites $L_{01}, L_{10}, L_{12}, L_{21}$ and zero amplitudes at the cube sites $C_{00}, C_{20}, C_{22}, C_{02}$ as shown in Fig. 1b. Clearly, on a Lieb lattice of $3M \times 3M$ sites, with M being the number of unit cells, there are in principle $(3M - 1) \times (3M - 1)$ such CLS, leading to the macroscopic FB degeneracy when M becomes large.

2.2. Sample fabrication

In order to translate this schematic into a viable experimental design for our chosen polymer, it should be noted that the spatial extent of a CLS around a plaquette can be argued to correspond to $a \sim \lambda/2$.¹ With the measured longitudinal speed of sound $c = 2380$ m/s in the chosen resin [41], and a target frequency of $f \sim 200$ kHz, we have $\lambda \sim 12$ mm. This indicated that the design of the Lieb lattice structures should have sub-cm values for a . Fabrication was performed using a high-resolution 3D printer (PHOTON MONO M5S [42], using ANYCUBIC standard clear resin [41]). The printer can achieve a minimum feature size of 0.2 mm. This is sufficiently fine for the chosen design requirements, with typical fabrication tolerances estimated at $\pm 0.1 - 0.2\%$. The mechanical properties of the printed resin correspond to a density of $\rho = 1100$ kg/m³, and a Young’s modulus of $Y = 1.4$ GPa [41].

The Lieb lattice being studied is a 2D structure [29,43], but a thin 3D-printed version would allow the excitation of out-of-plane guided acoustic modes in the third (perpendicular) direction. To suppress such modes and preserve effectively two-dimensional wave propagation, the structure was fabricated with a much larger extent in this direction, i.e., a height of $\Delta z = 20$ mm $\gg a$. Furthermore, the above construction of the FB relies on periodic boundary conditions. Since, periodic boundary conditions cannot be fabricated, instead we settle on a larger number of repeats of the unit cell shown in Fig. 2a. For reasons of stability and reproducibility during the 3D-printing process, we have chosen $M = 10$, i.e. our samples have $(M - 1) \times (M - 1) = 81$ plaquettes with $M \times M = 100$ cube sites and $2 \times (M \times M) = 200$ Lieb sites.

In order to couple an acoustic wave into the Lieb lattice, it was necessary to couple an ultrasonic transducer to one boundary of the lattice. Clearly, the coupling can depend on whether we attach this at the acoustic transmission channels, i.e. the hopping terms, or at the Lieb and cube sites. In Fig. 2a we show that we have defined four different boundaries: short (top) and long (R.H.S) acoustic channels, a thin layer of connected channels (bottom), and sites (L.H.S) to test their possible influence.

To see how the size of the Lieb unit cell determines the position of the acoustic FBs, two lattice structures were fabricated, both with $M = 10$, namely (i) one with $a = 4.32$ mm and (ii) a second one with a larger $a = 6.36$ mm (and thus potentially lower frequencies). This implies values for the diameter of the sites of $d = 1.08$ mm and $d = 1.59$ mm, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2c and d. The ratio of lattice constant and wavelength for the two lattices follows from the data provided and is $a/\lambda \sim 0.36$. With these values, it is expected that the FB frequencies would range from 100 kHz to 450 kHz.

¹ We note that another estimate based on the diagonals between Lieb sites results in a value of $a = \lambda/\sqrt{2}$. Apriori both are possible, depending on the chosen material system and defect lattice being studied. This highlights that these estimates should be a rough guide only.

Fig. 1. (a) Three-dimensional band structure of the Lieb lattice, plotted along the high-symmetry path $\Gamma - X - M - \Gamma$ as indicated by the white dashed line. The dispersive bands are green while the FB is purple. (b) Schematic diagram of the acoustic Lieb lattice. Circles (red & blue) indicate the lattice positions which support the pressure wave, and the acoustic channels between them are given as dashed lines. The smaller circles at the boundaries indicate the period extension. We have highlighted in blue the *cube* sites and in red the *Lieb* sites with C00, C02, C22, C20 and L01, L12, L21, L10 labeling the specific choices of cube (C_{xy}) and Lieb positions (L_{xy}). The black arrowed lines indicate the $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \gamma_4$ nearest-neighbour hopping parameters as used in the TB representation (1) and the black dashed box indicates the fundamental unit cell. Last, the integers at cube and Lieb sites show the normalized pressures for a CLS at the FB energy. (c) Non-dimensionalized band structure of the Lieb lattice computed via FEM simulations for the two Lieb geometries corresponding to $a = 4.32$ mm and $a = 6.36$ mm indicated by orange and blue circles, respectively. The three solid red lines represent the TB dispersion relation (1). The scales on the right hand side represent the corresponding dimensionalised frequency.

2.3. Measurement setup: Mounting and excitation

Experiments were conducted using a broadband piezoelectric ultrasonic transducer, with a center frequency $f_c = 300$ kHz. The full experimental arrangement is shown in Fig. 3. The samples were securely mounted in a way that minimises vibrational damping. The transducer source was coupled directly to one face of the sample using a thin film of ultrasonic gel to allow reproducible excitation while minimising additional damping.

The excitation consisted of a set of single-frequency tone bursts, with five cycles per frequency step, generated by a RITEC RPR4000 pulser unit. All spectra are interpreted in terms of relative, site-resolved am-

plitudes at fixed driving frequencies; no correction for the transducer's frequency response is required for this comparison.

The input power was set to 5% of the amplifier range so as to ensure a linear response of the structure. The transducer excited the Lieb lattice in its (x, y) plane, selecting the x direction without loss of generality.

Five different driving frequencies f_{freq} were chosen to capture the full band structure of the lattice. For the structure corresponding to $a = 4.34$ mm we choose these frequencies to be $f_{120} = 120$ kHz, $f_{200} = 200$ kHz, $f_{320} = 320$ kHz, $f_{420} = 420$ kHz and $f_{520} = 520$ kHz, while for the structure with $a = 6.36$ mm we have $f_{80} = 80$ kHz, $f_{150} = 150$ kHz, $f_{250} = 250$ kHz, $f_{400} = 400$ kHz and $f_{520} = 520$ kHz. Note that these are centre frequencies, with energy transmitted in each case across a rea-

Fig. 2. Fabricated acoustic Lieb lattice samples and corresponding geometric parameters. (a) Figure of the 3D-printed 10×10 Lieb lattice sample ($a = 4.32$ mm), with representative plaquettes highlighted for measurement. (b) Enlarged optical micrograph of a single plaquette showing labelled Lieb (L_{xy}) and cubic (C_{xy}) sites. (c) Unit-cell geometry, with cylinder diameter $d = 1.08$ mm, lattice spacing $L = 1.08$ mm, and connecting-strut width $w = 0.27$ mm. (d) Unit-cell geometry for the second lattice, featuring enlarged cylinders ($d = 1.59$ mm), spacing $L = 1.59$ mm, and strut width $w = 0.40$ mm. Both designs consist of solid polymer cylinders connected by thin rectangular struts, forming the three-site basis characteristic of the Lieb lattice.

sonable bandwidth. These driving frequencies were chosen to sample the dispersive bands, the predicted flat-band region, and the surrounding band gaps. In each lattice design, one frequency coincides with the expected flat-band frequency, while the remaining frequencies probe lower- and higher-frequency dispersive regimes, ensuring that the key features of the band structure are captured and allowing direct comparison between the two geometries.

We also measured c in a single *uniform* block of the sample resin material. We found $c = 2380 \pm 50$ m/s in good agreement with the value specified by the manufacturer of the resin material [41].

2.4. Measurement setup: Laser vibrometry and probing strategy

The out-of-plane particle velocity response at both Lieb and conventional cube site was measured at the sample surface using a Polytec OFV 5000 scanning laser vibrometer. To do this, a thin layer of adhesive reflective tape was applied on the surface at these sites. This enabled a reliable reflection of the probing laser beam. The tape thickness was kept at a minimal value so as not to either alter the mechanical boundary conditions or to introduce spurious resonances.

The vibrometer was laterally aligned and scanned manually across the different cube and Lieb sites, probing the out-of-plane vibrations of each. The laser spot size was tuned to closely match the site diameter in each structure, namely 1.08 mm and 1.59 mm (cf. Section 2.2). This choice ensured that overlap with neighboring sites was minimized to prevent the possibility of cross-talk.

The chosen acoustic Lieb lattices had mirror symmetry axes along their diagonals and along their central horizontal and vertical planes. These symmetries might have influenced the resulting acoustic wave patterns, similar to Chladni curves [44,45]. In order to check that our results were not influenced by these, we chose eight complete 'plaquettes' located across various positions in the Lieb lattices corresponding to a mix of positions with high and low symmetries. The positions are shown in Fig. 2a. In each plaquette, the sites were labelled as L_{xy} for Lieb sites and C_{xy} for cube sites. Here, x and y denote the local coordinates within each plaquette. By probing multiple plaquettes, we also ensured that the response characteristics were representative of intrinsic lattice physics rather than local fabrication variations.

In total, this corresponds to eight measurements for the four cube and four Lieb sites. With eight independent plaquettes, the four different boundary conditions, and the five excitation frequencies, this gives, $2 \times 4 \times 8 \times 4 \times 5 = 1280$ power spectra of the vibrational response for frequencies ranging from 80 to 600 kHz. We performed this whole set of measurements for lattice with $a = 4.32$ mm. For lattice $a = 6.36$ mm, we repeated the set, but this time only for 2 boundaries with the highest coupling.

3. Experimental power spectra

Signal acquisition was performed using a digital oscilloscope which collected time-domain data, which were averaged over 64 repetitions

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic of the experimental setup used to characterize the fabricated acoustic metamaterial. The arrangement enables pressure measurements at multiple points within the structure to evaluate its acoustic response. (b) Photograph of the experimental setup, illustrating the transducer mounted on the top surface of the sample.

to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio. The acquired signals were processed using a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) [46], so as to extract their frequency-domain characteristics.

Experiments were performed with our two lattices, i.e. those corresponding to $a = 4.32$ mm and $a = 6.36$ mm. In the following, we shall abbreviate these designs as D_4 and D_6 , respectively. A series of exemplary power spectra are shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that for D_4 , the driving frequency f_{200} couples strongest to the lattice at the Lieb sites (L_{01} , L_{10}), while at the cube sites (C_{00}), the frequencies f_{120} and f_{320} become prominent. The same pattern emerges for D_6 . Here it is the f_{150} excitation which is most enhanced on Lieb sites, while again the neighboring excitations of f_{80} and f_{250} are strong on the cube sites.

This tendency is consistent across all of the remaining measurements: the experimental spectra reveal three prominent resonance features, each seemingly corresponding to the three bands predicted by the TB dispersions (1): Close to the expected FB frequency, very enhanced vibrational amplitudes are observed at the Lieb sites (L_{xy}), while the cube sites (C_{xy}) show significantly reduced excitation. This strong site selectivity is a consistent signature of the CLSs, i.e. these states reside at the Lieb sites at particular frequencies only.

Furthermore, comparing the results of D_4 and D_6 demonstrates geometric scaling. We see that for D_4 the resonances occur at higher frequencies, with the CLS appearing at ≈ 200 kHz and the dispersive modes at ~ 120 kHz and ~ 320 kHz. On the other hand, for D_6 , the CLS resonances are at lower frequencies, with a FB at ≈ 150 kHz and the two dispersive bands appearing at ~ 80 kHz and ~ 250 kHz as shown in Fig. 4.

These differences between the vibrational responses of the Lieb and cube sites remain across all plaquettes in Fig. 2a, with only minor variations attributable to fabrication tolerances and finite-sample effects. These observations thus confirm the key spectral features: the frequency ranges of the bands, the site-selective localization, and the size-dependent scaling behaviour. These are also intrinsic to the lattice geometry rather than being artefacts of measurement location or surface variability.

We also found that, when changing the transducer position among the four different boundaries, the differences between the Lieb and cube sites persist, although the overall strength of the vibrational coupling into the lattice can vary.²

4. Discussion

The experimental measurements show a clear and consistent difference in the pattern of acoustic resonances between cube and Lieb site when exciting the D_4 and D_6 structures with different carrier frequencies. Vibrational amplitudes at the Lieb sites are significantly enhanced at the estimated FB frequencies, i.e. ~ 200 kHz for D_4 and 150 kHz for D_6 , while the cube sites remain at best only weakly excited.

In order to substantiate our findings further, we have performed acoustic finite element calculations of the resulting pressure fields in the chosen two geometries D_4 and D_6 . The details of the simulations are described in Appendix B. In Fig. 1c, the results for the FEM dispersion relation are shown to fit the three TB bands very well. The FEM analysis for D_4 reveals a nearly dispersionless band at 218.15 kHz. Similarly, the structure D_6 exhibits its FB at 149.2 kHz. These FEM values agree very well with the experimentally observed frequencies of the CLSs of the last section, i.e. the observed enhanced vibrational amplitudes at ≈ 200 kHz for D_4 and ≈ 150 kHz for D_6 .

Beyond the dispersion curves, the FEM eigenmodes reveal the spatial structure of the acoustic fields, allowing direct comparison with the experimentally measured site-selective responses. In linear acoustics, the particle velocity is proportional to the pressure gradient, $v \propto \nabla p$ [47–49], such that localized pressure eigenmodes correspond directly to localized surface velocities, allowing meaningful comparison between FEM pressure fields and vibrometer measurements (cf. Appendix C).

² For example, putting the transducer onto the (bottom) flat side in Fig. 4 seemed to couple into just the lower dispersive band than into the FB or the upper dispersive band.

Fig. 4. Power spectra for different excitation frequencies recorded at the positions L01, L10 and C00 at the bottom-left plaquette of Fig. 2a with transducer coupled to the top. (a) the D_4 and (b) the D_6 structures. The driving frequencies are indicated by the different colours and solid lines in each panel. The vertical dashed line in all figures denotes the FB energy estimated from the TB approach.

Fig. 5. Simulated acoustic pressure distributions for the Lieb lattice at the three high-symmetry points of the Brillouin zone. Rows correspond to (a-c) the upper dispersive band, (d-f) the flat band, and (g-i) the lower dispersive band. Columns show representative modes from the Γ point (left), the X point (central), and the M point (right). The flat-band modes (central row) exhibit the characteristic CLS pattern: pressure is concentrated on the Lieb sites while the central cube sites remain wave nodes.

Representative mode shapes at the Γ , X, and M points are shown in Fig. 5 for D_4 . The results for D_6 are similar.

At the FB frequency, we see that all three high-symmetry points display the characteristic structures of a CLS: the vibrational energy resides almost entirely on the Lieb sites, while the cube sites remain unexcited. The specific phase arrangements differ between Γ , X, and M, but the real-space confinement remains the same, reflecting the defining property of a FB, namely that its CLS eigenmodes are localized in real space for all wavevectors. The M-point (Fig. 5f) mode displays this most clearly: neighbouring Lieb sites oscillate out of phase, enforcing perfect destructive interference at the cube sites. Note that in photonic lattices, the phase relation of individual sites in a CLS has been explicitly measured with interferometry [50].

The FEM results also allowed us to establish the value of γ used in the TB calculations, and we find $\gamma = (62.5 \pm 0.5)$ kHz for D_4 and $\gamma = (43.5 \pm 0.5)$ kHz for D_6 . Furthermore, from the FEM calculations, we find higher bands, separated via a band gap varying from ≈ 400 kHz at the Γ point to ≈ 600 kHz around the M point. This width of the band gap is consistent with the absence of higher band modes in our experimental results shown in Fig. 4. Finally, the eigenmodes belonging to the dispersive bands show extended Bloch-like patterns, with significant excitation at the cube sites and smooth spatial variation across the lattice as shown in Fig. 5. These extended modes align with the broader resonances observed experimentally.

5. Conclusion

The experimental measurements provided comprehensive confirmation of FB behavior in the polymer-based acoustic Lieb lattices. The vibrometer scans reproduce not only the presence of strong resonances at the predicted FB frequencies, but also the emergence of band gaps and the characteristic site-selective localization of FB modes. In both samples, vibrational amplitudes at the Lieb sites are significantly enhanced at the FB frequency, while the cube sites remain weakly excited. This spatial contrast is a direct manifestation of the destructive interference mechanism associated with CLSs in the Lieb lattice. Although CLSs have been widely discussed in theoretical and photonic settings [50], the present results demonstrate their emergence in a fully three-dimensional, polymer-printed acoustic platform operating at ultrasonic frequencies.

It should be noted that the present work does not attempt a one-to-one numerical replication of the complete experimental set-up. Instead, the simulations provide a modal “fingerprint” that explains why certain lattice sites respond strongly at specific frequencies. The excellent qualitative agreement between simulated mode localization (Lieb versus cubic sites) and experimentally measured vibrational amplitudes confirms the validity of this approach.

Importantly, the comparison between the two fabricated geometries clearly highlights the tunability of the FB frequency. As the lattice constant increases, the entire spectrum shifts to lower frequencies, in agree-

ment with TB predictions. This geometric scaling establishes that frequency targeting does not require changing the material composition or resonance properties of individual elements. Instead, the dispersion can be engineered purely through lattice geometry, which is particularly advantageous for ultrasound technologies where operational frequencies must match transducer bandwidths, safety limits, and tissue penetration requirements [36,40].

The robustness of the observed localization further strengthens the physical interpretation. The FB signatures persist despite fabrication tolerances, small geometric irregularities, and damping in air. This resilience comes from how CLSs form: the waves cancel each other out along certain paths, which traps the energy in a small region. Because this cancellation doesn't rely on perfect geometry or materials, small changes to the structure do not easily break the FB mode [50]. Such robustness is essential for translating FB concepts from idealized lattices into practical metamaterial devices.

Note that the finite-sized samples are not expected to mask the key signatures of flat-band physics. In fact, the dominant localization peak remains clearly visible, its frequency shifts systematically with lattice geometry, and the strong contrast between Lieb and cubic sites is preserved throughout the sample.

Taken collectively, these results establish a coherent and experimentally verified picture of FB localization in 3D-printed acoustic Lieb lattices at ultrasonic frequencies. The demonstrated ability to engineer and tune FB modes through geometry alone, not through material composition, is a key advantage for wave-control technologies. Strong energy confinement at designated sites suggests practical pathways toward mode-selective excitation, enhanced imaging contrast, and frequency-selective sensing. Moreover, polymer-based fabrication enables rapid prototyping, low-cost production, and compatibility with aqueous coupling environments used in biomedical ultrasound [38]. These properties position Lieb-lattice-based metamaterials as promising candidates for future acoustic devices, from compact diagnostic components to programmable ultrasonic waveguides.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anusha Rehman: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization; **David Hutchins:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization; **Rudolf A. Römer:** Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization; **Peter J. Thomas:** Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization; **Katarzyna E. Sopińska:** Software, Methodology; **Jisun Im:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation; **Phillip Sheffield:** Resources, Investigation; **Stefano Laureti:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Calculation of the tight-binding dispersion relation

The 2D TB Hamiltonian for the unit cell can be written in momentum space as

$$\hat{H}(\vec{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} f_0 & \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 e^{-ik_x a} & \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 e^{-ik_y a} \\ \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 e^{ik_x a} & f_0 & 0 \\ \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 e^{ik_y a} & 0 & f_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\vec{k} = (k_x, k_y)$ represents the 2D wave vector, f_0 the resonant frequency of the PnC defects and γ_i , ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) the hopping strength as shown in Fig. 1b.

To derive the dispersion relation, we compute the eigenvalues of $H(\vec{k})$ via $\det([\hat{H}(\vec{k}) - f(\vec{k})\hat{I}]) = 0$.

This yields one flat band $f(\vec{k}) = f_0$, and two dispersive bands

$$f(\vec{k}) = f_0 \pm \sqrt{\gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2 + \gamma_3^2 + \gamma_4^2 + 2\gamma_1\gamma_2 \cos(k_x a) + 2\gamma_3\gamma_4 \cos(k_y a)} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

For the symmetric unit cell considered here in this text, the four nearest-neighbour couplings are taken equal, $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = \gamma_4 = \gamma$, resulting in Eq. (1), since the corresponding connections are geometrically equivalent; relaxing this assumption primarily alters the dispersive-band curvature without changing the existence of the flat band.

Appendix B. Finite-element modelling

We modelled the acoustic pressure field $p(\mathbf{r}, 2\pi f)$ inside the printed polymer as a homogeneous, isotropic medium described by the Helmholtz equation for pressure p [47] such that

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right) + \frac{4\pi^2 f^2}{\rho c^2} p = 0, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where the material parameters were taken as density $\rho = 1100 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and longitudinal sound speed $c = 2380 \text{ m/s}$ [41]. Attenuation and viscoelastic losses were neglected, an approximation appropriate for the sub-MHz regime considered here [51]. The surrounding air was omitted and treated as vacuum, justified by the large impedance contrast, which strongly suppresses acoustic leakage [52].

Finite-element simulations are carried out in COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS [47] using the *Pressure Acoustics, Frequency Domain* interface [47]. Single unit cells of the Lieb lattice are modelled using the specified fabricated sample geometries for D_4 and D_6 as shown in Fig. 2c and d.

To compute the dispersion relation, we use Bloch–Floquet periodic boundary conditions on opposite faces of the unit cell.

The Bloch wavevector \vec{k} was swept along the high-symmetry path Γ –X–M– Γ of the Brillouin zone to generate the band diagrams.

The physics-controlled tetrahedral mesh was defined such that the smallest elements corresponded to approximately ten elements per wavelength at the highest simulated frequency, resulting in 1594 elements for D_4 and 1578 elements for D_6 . Mesh-convergence tests verified that both eigenfrequency values and eigenmode shapes were insensitive to further refinement. The eigenfrequency solver relative tolerance was set to 10^{-30} to ensure numerical stability across both lattice geometries.

In addition to the periodic eigenfrequency calculations, we performed frequency-domain finite-element simulations on a 10×10 Lieb lattice for D_4 as shown in Fig. B.1. The finite structure was excited using a uniform background pressure field of 1 Pa applied at one boundary, while perfectly matched layers (PMLs) were implemented at the outer boundaries to suppress artificial reflections. This excitation generates a plane-wave that couples into the lattice in a manner analogous to the experimental transducer coupling.

Fig. B.1. Frequency-domain finite-element simulation of a 10×10 Lieb lattice excited by a uniform background pressure field applied at the left boundary. Perfectly matched layers (PMLs) are implemented at the input and output boundaries. The arrows indicate the direction of incident acoustic excitation. (b) Corresponding frequency response extracted at representative lattice sites, showing the absolute pressure amplitude at the cubic site C00 and the Lieb sites L01 and L10.

The resulting steady-state pressure fields and frequency responses exhibit strong localization at the Lieb sites near the flat-band frequency, alongside reduced transmission and enhanced attenuation, consistent with the experimentally observed site-selective vibrational enhancement. These simulations therefore provide a qualitative validation of the experimental observations and confirm that the measured responses originate from intrinsic flat-band physics rather than boundary-induced artifacts.

Appendix C. Relationship between pressure and velocity

We consider linear acoustic wave propagation in a homogeneous, isotropic medium at rest. Under the assumption of small-amplitude perturbations, the acoustic field is governed by the linearized equations of motion. The linearized momentum (Euler) equation reads [48,49]

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = -\nabla p(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where ρ_0 is the equilibrium mass density, $p(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the acoustic pressure, and $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the particle velocity.

Assuming time-harmonic fields of angular frequency ω ,

$$p(\mathbf{r}, t) = \Re\{\hat{p}(\mathbf{r})e^{i\omega t}\}, \quad \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \Re\{\hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{r})e^{i\omega t}\}, \quad (\text{C.2})$$

the momentum equation becomes, in the frequency domain,

$$i\omega\rho_0\hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{r}) = -\nabla\hat{p}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Rearranging yields the fundamental pressure–velocity relation,

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{i\omega\rho_0}\nabla\hat{p}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (\text{C.4})$$

This expression shows that the particle velocity is directly proportional to the spatial gradient of the acoustic pressure field. In particular, the normal component of the particle velocity at a surface is given by

$$v_n = \mathbf{v} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\frac{1}{i\omega\rho_0}\frac{\partial p}{\partial n}, \quad (\text{C.5})$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ denotes the outward surface normal.

This relation provides the physical basis for comparing finite-element pressure eigenmodes with laser Doppler vibrometry measurements. The vibrometer measures the out-of-plane surface velocity, which is proportional to the normal pressure gradient at the surface. Consequently, pressure-mode distributions computed using the

Pressure Acoustics interface in COMSOL Multiphysics directly encode the spatial structure of the experimentally observed vibrational response. Regions where the pressure gradient vanishes correspond to nodes in the measured velocity field, while strong localized pressure gradients give rise to enhanced vibrational amplitudes. This correspondence justifies the use of pressure-field mode shapes to interpret the site-selective velocity measurements reported in the main text.

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